

Characteristics of different 4-benzeneazo-isoxazoles are recorded in the following tables.

TABLE I

4-Substituted benzeneazo-3,5-dimethylisoxazoles (III R=R'=Me).

No.	R	%Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1	Phenyl	72	46°	Pale yellow	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ON ₃	N : 20.6%	20.0%
2	Anisyl	66	102°	Golden yellow	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃	N : 18.3	18.2
3	4-Bromophenyl	78	88°	Yellowish red	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ON ₃ Br	Br : 28.3	28.6
4	4-Chlorophenyl	77	54°	Light yellow	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ON ₃ Cl	Cl : 14.8	15.1
5	3-Chlorophenyl	74	65°	Light yellow	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ON ₃ Cl	Cl : 14.9	15.1
6	2-Chlorophenyl	74	72°	Golden yellow	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ON ₃ Cl	Cl : 15.2	15.1
7	4-Methylphenyl	68	76°	Golden yellow	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ ON ₃	N : 19.4	19.5
8	4-Nitrophenyl	79	108°	Pale yellow	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₄	N : 22.4	22.8

TABLE II

4-Substituted benzeneazo-3-methyl-5-phenylisoxazoles (III : R=Me; R'=Ph)

No.	R'	%Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1*	Phenyl	75	99°	Orange	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ON ₃	N : 15.6	15.0
2	4-Bromophenyl	81	136°	Golden yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ON ₃ Br	Br : 23.0	23.4
3	4-Chlorophenyl	79	111°	Golden yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ON ₃ Cl	Cl : 11.8	11.9
4	3-Chlorophenyl	74	98°	yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ON ₃ Cl	Cl : 11.7	11.9
5	2-Chlorophenyl	73	98°	Light yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ON ₃ Cl	Cl : 11.8	11.9
6	4-Methylphenyl	82	118°	Canary yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ON ₃	N : 15.4	15.2
7	3-Methylphenyl	70	88°	Orange	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ON ₃	N : 15.0	15.2

* Wittig, *et al. Ber.*, 1928, **61B**, 1140.

TABLE III

4-Substituted benzeneazo-3,5-diphenylisoxazoles (III : R=R'=Ph).

No.	R'	%Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1	Phenyl	76	123°	Orange-red	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ ON ₃	N : 12.7	12.9
2	4-Bromophenyl	81	141°	Orange-red	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ ON ₃ Br	Br : 19.6	19.8
3	4-Chlorophenyl	80	135°	Orange	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ ON ₃ Cl	Cl : 9.5	9.9
4	3-Chlorophenyl	77	120°	Golden yellow	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ ON ₃ Cl	Cl : 9.5	9.9
5	2-Chlorophenyl	76	99°	Orange-red	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ ON ₃ Cl	Cl : 9.9	9.9
6	4-Methylphenyl	64	155°	Pale yellow	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ ON ₃	N : 12.1	12.4
7	3-Methylphenyl	72	110°	Yellow	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ ON ₃	N : 12.0	12.4

Author's sincere thanks are due to Dr. S. S. Joshi of this college for his keen interest and the Government of India for the award of a scholarship.